

Mechanical Properties of Unidirectional C/C Composites Prepared Using Matrix Precursor Containing Green Coke as the Main Component

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ABSTRACT

Unidirectional C/C composites were prepared, without the conventional densification cycles, from prepreg sheets consisting of mesophase pitch-based carbon fiber with high or ultra-high modulus (FORCA FT-500 or FT-700, and with or without surface treatment), and a matrix precursor containing green petroleum coke as the main component. Effects of the properties of carbon fiber and the heat treatment temperature (HTT) were studied on mechanical properties such as tensile strength and interlamina shear strength (ILSS) of the composites. Above 1200°C the higher the HTT, the higher was the tensile strength of the C/C composite, regardless of the type of carbon fiber used, and reached a level of 800 - 900MPa at 2000°C and 2500°C, when the fiber volume fractions and bulk densities of the composites were between 42% and 48%, and between 1.71 and 1.85 g/cm³, respectively. The Young's modulus monotonically increased with increasing HTT for all four kinds of composite. On the other hand, below 2000°C, the higher the HTT, the higher was the ILSS. Above 2000°C, the ILSS decreased with an increase in the HTT. The maximum value of ILSS was 28MPa. These mechanical properties were considered from the interfacial behavior and the microstructure observed.

KEYWORDS: C/C Composites ; Unidirectional ; Tensile strength ; ILSS ; Fabrication.

1. INTRODUCTION

Approaching the 21st century, several new projects in the field of aerospace, similar to those in Europe, are under way in Japan. These include the Japanese HOPE space shuttle, space plane, SST and HST. The realization of these projects depends on the development of more advanced high performance structural materials in respect of high resistance to heat, abrasion and impact, as well as high specific strength and elasticity. Carbon/Carbon composite is one of the candidate materials

satisfying the requirements for these projects [1]. Recently many active studies have been reported to develop stronger and more elastic C/C composites [2-4].

In such C/C composites, if the matrix material exhibits a lower fracture strain than the reinforcement, the composite strength is determined by the fracture strain of the matrix. From a view-point of crack propagation from the matrix into the fiber, high modulus fiber is superior to high strength fiber for the reinforcement of carbon [5].

There are two established methods for forming the matrix to fabricate such C/C composites. One is impregnation with a thermosetting resin or a pitch with several subsequent densification cycles. The other is infiltration of chemical vapor deposition (CVD) carbon [6-7]. Either method needs much time to manufacture the final product and therefore costs a great deal.

We developed, then, the method for fabricating C/C composites without repeating steps of impregnation and carbonization. Furthermore, the mechanical properties of the unidirectional C/C composites prepared by a sheet lay-up processing method without several densification cycles were studied.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1. Materials

Four kinds of pitch-based carbon fiber were used for comparative evaluation. TABLE 1 lists the principal properties of the kinds of carbon fiber used. FT-500 fiber has a tensile modulus of about 500GPa and FT-700 fiber has that of about 700GPa. Letter N and Y of the fiber names mean without and with surface treatment, respectively. Every yarn consists of 3000 filaments. All fiber was supplied by TONEN Co., Ltd.

TABLE 1. Principal properties of carbon fibers

Grade	Diameter μm	Tensile strength GPa	Tensile modulus GPa	Fractue strain %	Note
FT700N	9.6	3.67	688	0.53	without surface treatment
FT700Y	9.7	3.28	699	0.47	with surface treatment
FT500N	10.1	3.23	563	0.57	without surface treatment
FT500Y	9.8	2.92	542	0.54	with surface treatment

The matrix precursor consists of 80wt% green petroleum coke and 20wt% solid resole type phenolic resin with alcoholic solvent. The mixture was ground for 3hrs in a planet type ball-mill. After milling, the mean diameter of each grain of green coke powder was about 1.3μm, and 40% of them were smaller than 1μm.

2.2. Fabricating Process of C/C Composite

C/C composites were fabricated according to the process as illustrated in Fig.1. Unidirectional fiber aligned prepreg sheets were prepared by winding a slurry-impregnated strand on to a drum. After drying in a vacuum oven at 65°C, the sheets were cut, stacked and pressed at a pressure of 20MPa at 150°C for an hour and post-cured at 170°C for a further hour. The cured composites had dimensions of 2-3mm thickness, 20mm width and 200mm length. Some were carbonized at 1200°C in a N₂ flow at atmospheric pressure and the remainder were graphitized at 2000°C and 2500°C in an Ar flow at atmospheric pressure. The heating and cooling rate was 1°C/min. in the carbonization treatment, and 10°C/min. in the graphitization treatment.

Fig.1 Steps in sheet lay-up processing of C/C composites

2.3. Mechanical test

The mechanical properties such as tensile strength and ILSS were measured on the unidirectional C/C composite specimens. The measuring methods are as shown in Fig.2. All the specimens were cut from the plates fabricated by the method described above.

In the tensile strength tests, both the ends of the specimens were reinforced with adhesively bonded Aluminum tabs, which can be easily gripped in the clamps of a universal testing machine.

Elongation was measured by a strain gauge attached to the center of the specimen. After the tensile tests, the fractured surface was observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM).

The ILSS test was conducted in accordance with the regulation of ASTM D-2344. Each of both the tests was carried out with 6 specimens on every types of composite at room temperature.

Fig.2 Schematic of test specimens

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The apparent density was calculated from the dimensions and weight of the specimens, and shown as a function of HTT in Fig.3. There is seen increase in apparent density with increasing HTT. The effects of Young's modulus and surface treatment of the carbon fibers on the composite density are not shown from these results.

Figure 4 shows the results of the tensile strength tests. This figure shows a marked decrease in tensile strength of

the composites having the surface treated fiber at an HTT of 1200°C. On the other hand, the tensile strength of composites containing fiber without surface treatment decreases only slightly or keeps the same level as before carbonization. Above 1200°C, the tensile strength increases with increasing HTT, reaching between 800 and 900MPa at HTTs of 2000°C and 2500°C.

Fig.3 Bulk density of C/C composites as function of HTT

Fig.4 Tensile strength of C/C composites as function of HTT

Figure 5 shows the relationship between HTT and Young's modulus of the composites. The Young's modulus monotonically increases with increasing HTT for all kinds of composite. Effects of the surface treatment of fiber on Young's modulus of composites are not shown. Below 2000°C, the Young's modulus of the composites with the FT700 fiber is higher than that with the FT500 fiber. At 2500°C, however, the values of Young's modulus for each kind of composite, with exception of the FT500Y, are the same, regardless of type of fiber used. As the fiber volume fraction of the composite using the FT500Y fiber and treated at 2500°C, is only 1.2 times higher than that of the others, the values of Young's modulus in all kinds of composite can be considered as almost the same. Figure 6 shows the relationship between HTT and fracture strain of the composites. At 1200°C, both the composites with the FT500 fiber and the FT700 fiber show the almost same strain value, though there is a marked difference in strain values between the composites having the fibers with and without surface treatment. At 2500°C, however, the values of the fracture strain in all kinds of composite are almost the same.

Fig.5 Tensile modulus of C/C composites as function of HTT

Fig.6 Fracture strain of C/C composites as function of HTT

Figure 7 shows the SEM observations of the fractured surfaces. A significant difference between fiber with surface treatment and fiber without surface treatments observed in the appearance of the composite surface. The fractured surfaces of the FT500Y and FT700Y composites are relatively smooth, showing almost no fiber pull-out. Such fracture surface indicates the occurrence of brittle fracture. On the other hand, many fiber pull-outs are observed in the FT500N and FT700N composites. The effects of the surface treatment of carbon fiber on the strength of C/C composites gaphitized at 2500°C are not clear from these photographs.

Figure 8 shows the ILSS test results. The effects of the kind of carbon fiber used on the ILSS are not clear from these results. Figure 9 shows the relationship between the apparent density and ILSS of the composites. The ILSS increases with increasing the density. On comparing composites whose densities are the same, the ILSS value for the composites carbonized at 1200°C is higher than those for the other composites. The value reaches about 25MPa when the density is 1.65 to 1.70g/cm³. The ILSS values have a tendency to decrease with increasing the HTT above 2000°C, in contrast to the tensile test results. The density values increase with increasing the HTT, and the maximum values of ILSS of the composites heat-treated at 1200°C, 2000°C and 2500°C are almost the same, in a region of 25MPa-29MPa. The density of the composite has a more considerable effect on the ILSS than on the tensile strength.

The microstructure of the matrix is shown in Fig.10. Many micro-pores are homogeneous distribute in the matrix, but no crack is observed, though there are many cracks in C/C composites that are fabricated by conventional densification method.

Fig.8 ILSS of C/C composites as function of HTT

Fig.9 ILSS as function of density

4. CONCLUSIONS

(1) A simple process for making unidirectional C/C composites was developed using low cost matrix precursor. The composites obtained by the process exhibit the following properties :

The apparent density, tensile modulus, tensile strength, and ILSS of the FT500Y composites, heat-treated at 2000°C, and with a volume fraction of 47 % are 1.71-1.79g/cm³, 287GPa, 811MPa, 28MPa, respectively.

(2) The bulk density and mechanical properties of unidirectional C/C composites prepared by this method were studied with respect to HTT and fiber properties. The conclusions obtained are as follows :

When the C/C composite was heat treated at 1200°C, the tensile strength was significantly affected by the surface treatment of carbon fiber used, and many fiber pull-out were observed in the fractured surface of the composites having higher strength.

Above 1200°C, the bulk density , tensile strength and Young's modulus of composites increased with increasing HTT.

The ILSS values have a tendency to decrease with increasing HTT above 2000°C, in contrast to the tensile test results

After graphitized at 2500°C, the properties of all four kinds of composite were independent of that of carbon fiber used.

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Fig.7 SEM photographs of fractured surfaces

Fig.10 SEM photographs of microstructure of matrix